

Ergonomic Assessment of Helmet for Young Adults in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

The use of an anthropometric method for product design and assessment is one of the most basic uses of ergonomics. The aim of this study is to develop an anthropometric database for head measurement and to design an ergonomic helmet using anthropometric methods. In this study, participants are consisted of 250 males and 250 females whose age range are 18 to 35. An anthropometric database of nineteen anthropometric measurements have been developed for both male and female in this study. Then make a comparison between those anthropometric data. Seven anthropometric measurements have been selected for helmet design. Then an ergonomic helmet is designed for both male and female young adults in Bangladesh. Anthropometric data are presented in this paper, and helmet size for proposed design is discussed.

Keywords: Ergonomics; Bangladesh; Head anthropometry; Helmet design.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Bangladesh, the motorcycle is the most cost-effective and commonly used means of transportation. For a variety of reasons, this is the most popular means of transportation. Low cost, higher fuel efficiency, smaller size for simpler parking in congested places, and high mobility transportation are just a few of the benefits.

Unfortunately, A large number of motorcycle accidents have occurred as a result of the widespread use of motorcycles [1]. According to the World Health Organization, Motorcycle riders account for more than 60% of traffic deaths, especially in low- and middle-income countries. [2]. In 2020, From January through October, at least 1,026 individuals died in 1,011 motorbike accidents across Bangladesh. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Every year, 2.17 million motorcyclists die in road accidents, with another 20 to 50 million injured [3]. Meanwhile, 353 incidents (34.91%) occurred as a result of 165 unique accidents (15.43 percent) resulted from head-on crashes, with additional vehicles hitting or running over them from behind. [4].

Young adults are the victims of the majority of motorcycle accidents in Bangladesh. Young adults are those who are eighteen to thirty-five years old [5]. A motorcycle collision can result in minor, moderate, or serious injuries. A high proportion of accidents are likely to be caused by a lack

of helmet use. In this situation, attempts have been made to limit the number of people killed in motorcycle accidents, including the requirement that anyone riding a motorcycle wear a helmet. Motorcycle helmets can help to decrease the number and severity of head injuries caused by collisions. [6]. In light of the possibility of mortality from a head injury [7]. Researchers discovered that helmeted riders had a 66 percent lower risk of intracranial damage than non-helmeted riders during the course of an 18-month motorcyclists who presented to a metropolitan trauma center in Sydney, Australia were studied. [1]. Helmet stability is critical for helmet performance because it ensures that the helmet provides adequate head coverage and stays in place during regular riding and in the case of a crash. Helmet roll-off has been linked to careless helmet retention strap modifications and poor fitment following crashes. Helmets aren't the best type of protection, although in a motorbike accident, they can avoid roughly 32% of head injuries [8]. This condition is typically tied to helmet size. Helmet manufacturers choose the current helmet size without consulting an anthropometric study, resulting in a wide range of helmet sizes depending upon head circumference. Given that head anthropometry isn't merely related to head diameter, It's unsurprising that the helmet size isn't suitable for most people. Bangladeshis do not yet have a standard size for helmets. Helmets must be made or altered for Bangladesh's young adults' comfort and stress reduction. The study's purpose is to assess

anthropometry and use the results to enhance helmet sizes because young adults are more likely to be involved in motorcycle accidents and suffer head injuries. The better a helmet fits motorcycle users, the more likely they will use it, minimizing the risk of brain injury.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Sample Design

The participants were young adults from Bangladesh. The age of young adults ranges from 18 to 35 years. Equation (1) was used to calculate the sample size [9]. The number of individuals picked at random, "n," is required to verify that a database's 5th and 95th percentiles accurately forecast the entire population's 5th and 95th percentiles with 95% confidence, and to calculate a percentage of relative accuracy using the formula:

$$n \geq (3.006 * CV/a)^2 \quad (1)$$

Where,

n= the estimated sample size

CV = coefficient of variation

a= the percentage of relative accuracy desired

$$CV=100*SD/\bar{x} \quad (2)$$

Where,

CV = coefficient of variation;

SD = Standard Deviation

\bar{x} = mean of a population

The minimal sample size "n" was calculated to be 468 using the maximum coefficient of variation value from similar research [10] (CV = 7.19, as SD = 3.93, and Mean = 54.63, among the populations studied in this research), and the relative accuracy of 1%. As a consequence, the authors selected 500 male and female volunteers to participate in the study.

2.2 Instrumental Selection

The required instruments for anthropometric measurements are:

1. Martin anthropometer
2. Spreading caliper

The anthropometric dimensions were taken using these instruments. Most of the measurements were obtained while standing and sitting with their feet flat on the floor. Before any measurements were taken, all of the equipment was calibrated against accepted standards. The measurements were taken several times to avoid any kind of error. The measurements were obtained in inches and then converted to centimeters.

2.3 Statistical Analysis

The descriptive statistics were summarized using the software SPSS version 25 in terms of standard deviation, mean, and different percentile values (5th, 25th, 50th, 75th, and 95th). To find the differences between measurements, "t" values, "p" values were calculated. Moreover, a head measurement comparison between Bangladeshi male and female young adults has been developed.

2.4 Anthropometric Measurements

Nineteen dimensions of head anthropometry were measured including (1) Head circumference, (2) Bitrignon coronal arc, (3) Bitrignon frontal arc, (4) Bitrignon subnasale arc, (5) Bitrignon chin arc, (6) Bitrignon submandibular arc, (7) Head breadth, (8) Head length, (9) Bigonial breadth, (10) Menton to top of the head, (11) Head thickness, (12) Tragion top of head, (13) Bitrignon breadth, (14) Bizygomatic breadth, (15) Diametric menton to back of the head, (16) Nose to top of the head, (17) Pronasale to eye, (18) Face breadth, (19) Eye to back of the head as can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Anthropometric dimensions of human head

2.4 Anthropometric Measurements for Helmet Design

Seven measurements have been selected among nineteen measurements for helmet design These are: Head breadth, Menton to top of the head, Diametric menton to back of the head, Nose to top of the head, Pronasale to eye, Face breadth, and Eye to back of the head.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Anthropometric measurements of male population

Anthropometric measurements (cm)	Mean	Standard Deviation	Max	Min	5 th Percentile	50 th Percentile	95 th Percentile
Head circumference	56.59	3.19	65.95	49.13	51.03	56.63	61.51
Bitracion coronal arc	35.93	2.12	42.21	30.46	32.42	36.02	39.49
Bitracion frontal arc	30.25	1.81	36.27	25.56	27.18	30.37	33.29
Bitracion subnasale arc	29.43	1.68	33.90	25.06	26.54	29.42	32.07
Bitracion chin arc	32.80	1.93	38.25	28.00	29.44	32.92	35.84
Bitracion submandibular arc	30.06	1.96	35.61	25.15	26.74	30.05	33.29
Head breadth	17.22	1.33	20.68	14.25	15.09	17.16	19.58
Head length	18.64	1.35	22.85	15.23	16.47	18.61	20.91
Bigonial breadth	11.87	0.99	14.79	9.33	10.35	11.80	13.61
Menton to top of the head	22.63	1.35	26.36	19.16	20.48	22.58	24.82
Head thickness	19.54	1.29	23.74	16.49	17.39	19.55	21.45
Tracion top of head	14.13	1.17	17.36	11.44	12.41	14.06	16.10
Bitracion breadth	13.83	1.26	16.91	11.05	11.88	13.76	15.84
Bizygomatic breadth	14.10	1.11	17.36	11.54	12.40	14.02	15.85
Diametric menton to back of the head	26.19	1.93	31.02	21.21	23.11	26.25	29.32
Nose to top of the head	15.93	1.18	19.29	13.04	13.90	16.00	17.76
Pronasale to eye	20.60	1.69	26.11	16.58	17.96	20.48	23.26
Face breadth	17.21	1.40	21.21	13.76	15.04	17.10	19.52
Eye to back of the head	18.46	1.24	22.19	15.42	16.42	18.35	20.47

Table 2 : Anthropometric measurements of Female population

Anthropometric measurements (cm)	Mean	Standard Deviation	Max	Min	5 th percentile	50 th percentile	95 th percentile
Head circumference	55.26	3.88	64.90	45.42	48.63	55.28	61.51
Bitracion coronal arc	35.42	2.69	42.83	28.80	31.36	35.55	40.10
Bitracion frontal arc	26.39	2.41	33.66	20.73	22.84	26.04	30.34
Bitracion subnasale arc	24.83	1.80	29.46	20.43	21.86	24.84	27.74
Bitracion chin arc	29.28	2.19	35.19	22.71	25.38	29.37	32.60
Bitracion submandibular arc	28.39	2.30	35.63	23.28	24.40	28.42	32.43
Head breadth	17.13	1.40	21.36	13.17	14.70	17.18	19.39
Head length	16.63	1.58	20.94	12.72	14.12	16.64	19.17
Bigonial breadth	10.52	1.12	13.16	8.01	8.89	10.41	12.44
Menton to top of the head	22.76	1.87	28.48	17.94	19.65	22.77	25.88
Head thickness	19.35	2.28	24.59	14.28	15.85	19.30	23.15
Tracion top of head	14.39	1.10	17.48	11.35	12.65	14.44	16.23
Bitracion breadth	13.23	1.25	16.15	9.99	11.18	13.16	15.33
Bizygomatic breadth	13.48	1.09	16.24	10.45	11.80	13.44	15.23

Diametric menton to back of the head	25.66	2.20	31.07	19.98	22.16	25.66	29.34
Nose to top of the head	15.98	1.57	19.98	12.38	13.49	15.86	18.65
Pronasale to eye	20.09	1.71	24.51	16.13	17.11	20.16	23.14
Face breadth	16.06	1.37	19.48	12.72	13.93	16.01	18.39
Eye to back of the head	17.97	1.63	22.71	13.84	15.20	17.95	20.56

Table 3: Comparison of anthropometric data between Bangladeshi male and female

Male				Female			(t-value & p-value)	
Variable	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	t -value	p -value
Head breadth	250	17.22	1.33	250	17.13	1.4	0.804	0.422
Menton top of the head	250	22.63	1.35	250	22.76	1.87	0.933	0.351
Diametric menton to back of the head	250	26.19	1.93	250	25.66	2.2	2.852	0.005
Nose to top of the head	250	15.93	1.18	250	15.98	1.57	0.361	0.718
Pronasale to eye	250	20.6	1.69	250	20.09	1.71	3.406	0.001
Face breadth	250	17.21	1.4	250	16.06	1.37	9.286	0
Eye to back of the head	250	18.46	1.24	250	17.97	1.63	3.79	0

*Statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$, ($p < 0.05$)

Table 4: Associated helmet dimensions with anthropometric measurements

Helmet Dimensions	Anthropometric Measurements	Measurements					
		Male			Female		
		5 th percentile	50 th percentile	95 th percentile	5 th percentile	50 th percentile	95 th percentile
Helmet width	Head breadth	15.09	17.16	19.58	14.70	17.18	19.39
Helmet height	Menton to top of the head	20.48	22.58	24.82	19.65	22.77	25.88
Helmet diameter	Diametric menton to back of the head	23.11	26.25	29.32	22.16	25.66	29.34
Glass helmet height	Nose to top of the head	13.90	16.00	17.76	13.49	15.86	18.65
Helmet glass length	Pronasale to eye	17.96	20.48	23.26	17.11	20.16	23.14
The width of the front of the helmet	Face breadth	15.04	17.10	19.52	13.93	16.01	18.39
Helmet length	Eye to back of the head	16.42	18.35	20.47	15.20	17.95	20.56

Tables 1 and 2 indicate the anthropometric head dimensions for young adult samples, respectively, for men and women. Mean value, Standard deviation value, Maximum value, Minimum value and Percentile values (5th, 50th, 95th) are included in these tables.

In table 3, Seven types of measurement are selected among nineteen anthropometric measurements for designing the helmet. A comparison has been done by t-test using p-values to identify the difference of anthropometric measurements for male and female to decide the variation of design for both gender. There has been found significant differences among three measurements ($p < 0.05$). These are Pronasale to eye, Face breadth, Eye to back of the head.

That's why two different types of helmet should be designed for two gender because of having significant differences among anthropometric measurements. Associated helmet dimensions with anthropometric measurements have been shown in table 4.

Table 5: Proposed helmet size for male

Helmet Dimensions	Helmet Size (cm)		
	S	M	L
Helmet width	15.09	17.16	19.58
Helmet height	20.48	22.58	24.82
Helmet diameter	23.11	26.25	29.32
Glass helmet height	13.90	16.00	17.76
Helmet glass length	17.96	20.48	23.26
The width of the front of the helmet	15.04	17.10	19.52
Helmet length	16.42	18.35	20.47

There are various techniques for calculating a product's standard size, the most common of which is based on percentiles [11]. Percentile statistics are a type of order statistics that can be used to estimate the percentage of data that should fall above and below a certain value [12]. To determine the standard size of helmet, percentile method has been used where 5th, 50th and 95th percentile indicates reference size S, M and L respectively. So, in this study, 5th percentile value is used for reference size S, 50th percentile value is used for reference size M and 95th percentile value is used for reference size L for helmet design.

Table 6: Proposed helmet size for female

Helmet Dimensions	Helmet Size (cm)		
	S	M	L
Helmet width	14.70	17.18	19.39
Helmet height	19.65	22.77	25.88
Helmet diameter	22.16	25.66	29.34
Glass helmet height	13.49	15.86	18.65
Helmet glass length	17.11	20.16	23.14
The width of the front of the helmet	13.93	16.01	18.39
Helmet length	15.20	17.95	20.56

Table 5 and 6, the helmet size for designing a helmet associated with helmet dimensions are shown. Table 5 is for male population and table 6 is for female population. Figure 2 shows the proposed helmet design for both male and female young adults of Bangladesh.

Fig. 2: Helmet design for male and female

4. CONCLUSION

The number of motor bike is increasing in a large scale around the world. The matter of safety is also an essential topic for the driver. Helmet is the vital thing to use during

driving. As it is necessary for the biker, So it should be fit and comfortable to use. The main focus of the study is to make a fit and comfortable helmet for the young adults of Bangladesh. That's why an agronomical helmet has been designed for the Bangladeshi young adults who use bike to ride.

Nineteen anthropometric data of 500 of both male and female young adults of Bangladesh have been taken. The age of young adults ranges from 18 to 35 years. The measurements were collected to design the helmet. Seven anthropometric measurements have been selected among nineteen measurements to design the helmet. The measurements are Head breadth, Diametric menton to back of the head, Menton to top of the head, Nose to top of the head, Face breadth, Pronasale to eye, Eye to back of the head. An anthropometric database has been developed for young adults of both male and female. The database contains average value, maximum value, minimum value, standard deviation and 5th percentile, 50th percentile, 95th percentile value. The helmet has been designed using percentile method. 5th, 50th and 95th percentile indicates reference size S, M and L of helmet respectively. There has been significant difference between male and female among three anthropometric measurements of Bangladesh. That's why the helmet has been designed for both male and female.

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